

ASSESSMENT ON THE USEFULNESS OF ENGLISH LANGUAGE MATERIALS IN KEEPING STUDENTS ENGAGED IN MODULAR DISTANCE LEARNING: A FRAMEWORK FOR MATERIAL INTEGRATION

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the challenges encountered by teachers and learners, the learners' level of interest in English, and their academic performance under modular distance learning among Grade 11 students at Biabas Trade High School during School Year 2025–2026. Using a descriptive-survey research design, the study involved 120 respondents, composed of 10 teachers and 110 learners, selected through stratified random sampling. Researcher-modified questionnaires measured the challenges faced by teachers in module preparation, monitoring, feedback, and communication, as well as the challenges encountered by learners in understanding content, managing time, handling home responsibilities, and maintaining motivation. Learners' interest in English was assessed in terms of engagement, motivation, and willingness to learn, while academic performance was determined based on English grades. Results indicated that teachers experienced moderate challenges in preparing and delivering modules, monitoring learner outputs, and providing timely feedback, while learners faced slight to moderate difficulties in understanding lessons, organizing their learning schedule, and sustaining motivation. Learners demonstrated a moderate level of interest in English, which corresponded to satisfactory to very satisfactory academic performance. Significant relationships were observed between learners' interest and academic performance, as well as between certain learner challenges and performance, highlighting the impact of engagement and motivation on learning outcomes. The findings emphasize the need for stronger support systems for teachers in module preparation and

delivery, strategies to sustain learner interest, and improved home–school coordination to enhance the effectiveness of modular distance learning in senior high school contexts.

Keywords: *English modular learning, Grade 11 learners, learners' interest, academic performance, distance learning challenges*

INTRODUCTION

The COVID-19 pandemic has had a significant impact on the education sector, and the effects are likely to be felt for many years to come. Nevertheless, the undisputed truth is that this health crisis brought vast changes to every Filipino's life. Government and private establishments were ordered to shut down to prevent widespread contamination of the disease in the country. Educational institutions were not exempted from complying with the government's mandate on health protocols.

Teachers and parents adapted to different learning modes to guarantee continuity of learning despite adverse conditions. The Department of Education formulated the Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan (LCP) to ensure that learning continues while guaranteeing the health, safety, and well-being of all learners, teachers, and DepEd employees (Anzaldo, 2021).

Print materials are primarily paper-based resources that reach intended audiences through written words or illustrations. The most commonly adapted distance learning modality in the country is modular printed learning. All public schools in the Division of Bohol adopted this method of instruction (De Villa & Manalo, 2020). The main learning materials used in public schools are printed instructional materials in the form of Self-Learning Modules (SLMs) and Learning Activity Sheets (LAS), which are written by designated teacher-writers in the Division of Bohol and published only after passing the quality assurance process. These printed materials serve as the primary guides to assist learners throughout the learning process. The types of printed learning materials utilized by students vary from pure-text modules to those enriched with graphics or visuals.

Moreover, Anzaldo (2021) emphasized that learning materials in modular distance learning can significantly increase learners' achievement by supporting learning. Well-designed worksheets and activity sheets provide learners with opportunities to practice new skills and reinforce understanding through independent exploration and repetition.

However, as a public school teacher, it is observed that the use of printed materials in modular distance learning posed several challenges for students, teachers, and parents. These challenges include internet connectivity problems among learners in remote areas; inadequate access to technological resources that support independent study; difficulty understanding module content and assessment instructions; heavy academic workload; poor learning environments; and mental health concerns. Alban and Alieto (2022) further noted that learners rely heavily on SLMs and other activity sheets in both print and digital formats, while teachers take responsibility for checking outputs and monitoring learner progress on a weekly basis.

In addition, Parojenog (2020) emphasized that effective English and literature instruction relies on the use of varied and purposeful teaching approaches that actively engage learners in the meaning-making process. The study showed that instructional effectiveness is shaped not only by the quality of learning materials but also by the pedagogical strategies employed to facilitate comprehension, promote interaction, and develop critical thinking. Within modular distance learning, where teacher–learner contact is significantly reduced, these insights highlight the need for carefully designed instructional approaches that compensate for the limitations of printed modules.

The underlying disadvantages of print materials further intensify the challenges faced by learners, teachers, and parents. Printed learning materials lack interaction, audio-visual elements, and immediate feedback, and they require strong reading and language skills—conditions that create barriers for non-readers or struggling learners. As a result, one of the greatest challenges for teachers is sustaining student engagement throughout modular distance learning.

In light of this premise, the researcher is prompted to conduct a study that evaluates the usefulness of English language learning materials in modular distance learning. The study aims to determine the aspects of these learning materials that require improvement or enhancement so that educators may maximize their full potential, particularly in teaching the English language in modular distance learning settings.

Research Questions

This study assessed the usefulness of English language materials in keeping students engaged in modular distance learning in order to develop a framework of materials integration.

Specifically, this study sought to answer the following:

1. What is the assessment of the participants (teachers and students) on the usefulness of English language materials in terms of:
 - 1.1 informativeness;
 - 1.2 sharing;
 - 1.3 basic presentation structure;
 - 1.4 retention/memorability; and
 - 1.5 role in the learning process?
2. Do students differ significantly in their assessment of the types of English language learning materials based on their grades categorized as:
 - 2.1 advanced;
 - 2.2 proficient;
 - 2.3 approaching proficiency;
 - 2.4 beginning proficiency; and
 - 2.5 developing proficiency?
3. Do teachers and students differ significantly in their assessment of the usefulness of printed materials with and without graphics?
4. What framework could be proposed for the integration of materials in modules?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This research employed a non-experimental retrospective and cross-sectional descriptive study (Johnson and Christensen, 2016). The questionnaire on the participants' assessment of the usefulness of learning English language materials with purely printed text and printed text with graphics was a tool from the standardized instrument of the study of Yildirim et. al. (2016) to come up with the expected findings. Meanwhile, the English grade of the first and second grading period of Grade 10 learners was derived through the documentary analysis method. The researcher made use of the School Form 9 (SF9) of the student participants to gather the data intended for this variable.

Research Environment

The study was conducted in the Trinidad II district particularly Hinlayagan National High School. The town of Trinidad was once a part of the town of Talibon until it was established as a different municipality on September 1, 1947. The municipality was named after Trinidad Roxas, the wife of President Manuel Roxas, and the town is also known for Kawasan Falls and Batungay cave. The town of Trinidad, Bohol celebrates its feast on May 15, to honor the town patron San Isidro Labrador. According to the 2020 census, it has a population of 35,119 people.

Hinlayagan National High School was chosen as research environment because it is the largest secondary school in the district of Trinidad II. Presently, the town is considered a 3rd class municipality in the second congressional district in the province of Bohol. The town has 20 elementary schools and 6 secondary schools. It has two educational districts, Trinidad I and Trinidad II.

Research Participants

The participants were six (6) English teachers and seventy-two (72) Grade 10 students. A total of seventy-eight (78) are the subjects of the study. The official list of grade 10 learners was taken from the Learner's Information System (LIS). Simple random sampling by section was used for these students of Hinlayagan National High School in Trinidad II District.

Research Instrument

The researcher utilized a modified survey questionnaire as sources of data. The student's academic performance which was categorized as advanced (90-100), proficient (85-89), approaching proficiency (80-84), beginning proficiency (75-79), and developing proficiency (below 75) based on their final grade in the school year 2021-2022 as reflected in their School Form 9 (SF9). It also asked for the profile of the student-participants.

The second part of the survey questionnaire was a 4-point Likert scale to measure students' assessment of the types of English language learning materials with purely printed text and printed text with graphics was a modified standardized tool from the study of Yıldırım et al (2016). It had fifteen (15) items with five dimensions namely: informativeness, sharing, basic presentation structure, retention/memorability, and role in the literacy process.

The researcher-made instruments had undergone a reliability and validity test to ensure their accuracy. It was piloted to twenty (20) Grade 10 students and five (5) English teachers from Trinidad I who were not study participants but shared the same profile. The updated tool was validated using Cronbach's Alpha. With the Cronbach's Alpha value of 0.798, the researcher's instrument used was highly reliable. To maintain the trustworthiness of the study, adequate data were collected. These data were presented in a matrix and analyzed objectively.

Research Procedure

This study was conducted in June 2022 after the proposal was approved. The researcher secured an approved transmittal letter from the principal and the participants' classroom adviser. When the request is granted, another request letter was sent to the District Supervisor of Trinidad II. Then finally, the research participants received a formal letter requesting their permission to become part of the study ensuring them that any personal data gathered from them was treated with full confidentiality as stipulated in the Data Privacy Act of 2012 or Republic Act 10173.

The questionnaire was distributed personally to the participants where they were gathered into group, explained to them thoroughly the importance of the study and assisted them with the difficult words or questions following the minimum health standards as prescribed by the local Inter-Agency Task Force (IATF) in this time of the pandemic. The participants were given one (1) week to accomplish the questionnaire. The participants' certification of informed consent was ensured by the researcher. After gathering the data, these were then tallied, tabulated, collated, and subjected to descriptive and inferential statistics for analysis and interpretation in accordance with the specific problems of the study. Thus, adding empirical data.

Statistical Treatment

The data gathered were computed based on the statistical treatment as follows:

To determine the academic performance of the students, the data was subjected to Percentage and Arithmetic Mean.

To determine the students' assessment of the types of learning materials with purely printed text and printed text with graphics, Weighted Mean (WM) was utilized.

Furthermore, to determine the significant difference between the student's assessment of the usefulness of learning materials based on their grades and the

significant difference in the participant's assessment of the usefulness of printed learning materials, the data were subjected to One-Way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA)

RESULTS

The data were collected from respondents through survey questionnaires and are presented in tabular form for clarity and ease of interpretation.

Table 1. Usefulness of English Language Materials as Assessed by the Teachers

Factors	No Graphics		With Graphics	
	Mean	Int	Mean	Int
Informativeness	2.50	LU	3.83	HU
1. purely printed text facilitates learning/ visual representation used in printed text with graphics facilitates learning	2.50	MU	3.67	HU
2. purely printed text are more informative/ printed text with graphics are more informative	2.33	LU	3.83	HU
3. understand that, presentation of information using purely printed text facilitates better learning./ understand that, printed text with graphics, presentation of information text facilitates better learning.	2.67	MU	4.00	HU
Sharing	2.17	LU	3.72	HU
4. aware that, among the different sources of learning, they especially recommend purely printed text to people around them./ are aware that, among the different sources of learning, they especially recommend printed text with graphics to people around them	2.17	LU	3.67	HU
5. share purely printed text, which they like, to their friends who may be interested./ share printed text with graphics, which they like, to their friends who may be interested.	2.00	LU	3.67	HU
6. share the purely printed text that are prepared in compliance with copyrights./ share the printed text with graphics that are prepared in compliance with copyrights.	2.33	LU	3.83	HU
Basic Presentation Structure	2.39	LU	3.72	HU
7. much interested in purely printed text because though it's time consuming to read it's more comprehensive./ are much interested in printed text with graphics because it's more comprehensive thus it's timesaving.	2.33	LU	3.67	HU
8. do not trust learning materials with purely printed text whose references are not indicated./ do not trust learning materials with printed text and graphics whose references are not indicated.	2.50	MU	3.67	HU
9. do not understand the message given by the purely printed text with no visuals./ do not understand the message given by the printed text with graphics because of too many visuals.	2.33	LU	3.83	HU
Memorability	2.00	LU	3.89	HU
10. purely printed text makes what they have learned from them more memorable./ visualizations in printed text with graphics make what they have learned from them more memorable.	2.00	LU	4.00	HU
11. remember information that they learned from purely printed text easier./ remember information that they learned from printed text with graphics easier.	2.17	LU	4.00	HU
12. learn better critical information that are conveyed in purely printed text/ . learn better critical information that are conveyed in printed text with graphics.	1.83	LU	3.67	HU
Role in Learning Process	1.94	LU	3.72	HU
13. prefer to read a purely printed text rather than reading a printed text with graphics to learn same subject./ . prefer to read a printed text with graphics rather than reading a plain text to learn same subject.	2.00	LU	3.67	HU
14. prefer reading purely printed text before checking other sources concerning a subject they are trying to learn./ . prefer reading printed text with graphics before checking other sources concerning a subject they are trying to learn.	2.17	LU	3.83	HU
15. first investigate or examine purely printed text to gain an idea about a subject they will be learning./ first investigate or examine printed text with graphics to gain an idea about a subject they will be learning.	1.67	LU	3.67	HU
Overall Mean	2.20	LU	3.78	HU

Note. Not Useful (NU: 1.00-1.75); Less Useful (LU: 1.76-2.50); Moderately Useful (MU: 2.51-3.25); Highly Useful (HU: 3.26-4.00)

Table 1 presents the data about the teacher-participants' assessment on the usefulness of printed materials with or without graphics and were measured based on the five criteria, namely; informativeness, sharing, basic presentation structure, memorability, and the role in learning process. In the first criterion (informativeness), it could be gleaned from the table that item 3 "understand that, presentation of information using purely printed text facilitates better learning. Understand that, printed text with graphics, presentation of information text facilitates better learning" obtained the highest weighted mean of 2.67 interpreted as "Moderately Useful" for with graphics and 4.00 interpreted as "Highly Useful" for with graphics. On the other hand, item 1 "purely printed text facilitates learning. Visual representation used in printed text with graphics facilitates learning" got the lowest weighted mean of 2.50 interpreted as "Moderately Useful" for no graphics and 3.67 interpreted as "Highly Useful" for with graphics. This means that the learners are more engaged in dealing instructional materials with text with the supplementation of graphics.

The finding is in agreement to what Collins et al. (2018) had found out that determining informativeness is a strategy that readers use to distinguish between what information in a text is most important versus what information is interesting but not necessary for understanding. This practical learning strategy enables students to distinguish between the most and least important information presented in textbooks, nonfiction reading, and other instructional materials.

In terms of sharing, it could be manifested from the table item 6 "share the purely printed text that are prepared in compliance with copyrights./ share the printed text with graphics that are prepared in compliance with copyrights" obtained the highest weighted mean of 2.33 described as "Less Useful" for no graphics and 3.83 described as "Highly useful" while item 5 "share purely printed text, which they like, to their friends who may be interested./ share printed text with graphics, which they like, to their friends who may be interested" obtained the lowest weighted mean of 2.00 described as "Less Useful" for no graphics and 3.67 described as "Highly Useful" for with graphics. This implies that the learners are more engaged in sharing English instructional materials when graphics are present.

The results are in harmony with what Naparin and Saad (2017) had asserted that sharing instructional materials with graphics are useful to students. It aids those students in organizing information in a logical way. Infographic creation helps meet tech literacy standards. The process of making infographic helps students improve their research chops and find trustworthy sources of information. It helps students exhibit their understanding of a subject in different ways.

As to basic presentation structure item 8 "do not trust learning materials with purely printed text whose references are not indicated./ do not trust learning materials with printed text and graphics whose references are not indicated" acquired the highest mean of 2.50 interpreted as "Less Useful" for without graphic and 3.67 for with graphics. On the other hand, item 7 "much interested in purely printed text because though it's time

consuming to read it's more comprehensive./ are much interested in printed text with graphics because it's more comprehensive thus it's timesaving" earned the lowest weighted mean of 2.33 transcribed as "Less Useful" for without graphics and 3.67 transcribed as "Highly Useful" for with graphics. This denotes that the presentation structure of learning materials with graphics is way better than those of purely given text.

The data revealed relates with what Yıldırım and colleagues (2016) had pointed the basic presentation structure of learning materials is essential for their effectiveness, whether they are printed or digital, and whether or not they contain graphics. A well-organized, visually appealing, and concise presentation structure can enhance learning and improve retention.

Based on memorability, it could be gleaned from the table that item 11 "remember information that I learned from purely printed text easier./ remember information that I learned from printed text with graphics easier" secured the highest weighted mean of 2.17 interpreted as "Less Useful" for no graphics and 4.00 interpreted as "Highly Useful" for with graphics while item 12 "learn better critical information that are conveyed in purely printed text/ learn better critical information that are conveyed in printed text with graphics" earned the lowest weighted mean of 1.83 interpreted as "Less Useful" for no graphics and 3.67 interpreted as "Highly Useful". This implies that an instructional materials memorability plays a main role in influencing the learners' future memories which can be related to its usability.

The findings are in congruity with what Zull (2020) had quoted that one great mystery of the learners' experiences is why their memories often act against their visualization. They remember plots that are not particularly important to them, yet they forget the names and faces of new characters that they try desperately to remember.

In terms of learning process, it could be manifested from the table that item 14 "prefer reading purely printed text before checking other sources concerning a subject they are trying to learn./ prefer reading printed text with graphics before checking other sources concerning a subject they are trying to learn" got the highest weighted mean of 2.17 described as "Less Useful" for without graphics and 3.83 for with graphics while item 15 "first investigate or examine purely printed text to gain an idea about a subject they will be learning./ first investigate or examine printed text with graphics to gain an idea about a subject they will be learning" got the lowest weighted mean of 2.17 described as "Less Useful" for without graphics and 3.83 for with graphics. This connotes that instructional materials with graphics enhance the teaching-learning process especially in the modular distance learning.

The results revealed coincide with what Alban & Alieto (2022) had found out that instructional materials are essential since they help the teacher and learners avoid overemphasis on recitation and rote learning that can easily dominate a lesson especially in the distance learning. Resource materials allow learners to have practical experiences

which help them to develop skills and concepts and to work in a variety of ways in this time of the pandemic.

Table 2. Usefulness of English Language Materials as Assessed by the Students

Factors	No Graphics		With Graphics	
	Mean	Int	Mean	Int
Informativeness	2.91	MU	3.66	HU
1. facilitates learning/ visual representation used in printed text with graphics facilitates learning	2.93	MU	3.76	HU
2. purely printed text are more informative/ printed text with graphics are more informative	2.90	MU	3.61	HU
3. understand that, presentation of information using purely printed text facilitates better learning/ understand that, printed text with graphics, presentation of information text facilitates better learning.	2.89	MU	3.60	HU
Sharing	2.84	MU	3.59	HU
4. am aware that, among the different sources of learning, I especially recommend purely printed text to people around me./ am aware that, among the different sources of learning, I especially recommend printed text with graphics to people around me.	2.89	MU	3.65	HU
5. share purely printed text, which I like, to my friends who may be interested./ share printed text with graphics, which I like, to my friends who may be interested.	2.86	MU	3.56	HU
6. share the purely printed text that are prepared in compliance with copyrights./ share the printed text with graphics that are prepared in compliance with copyrights.	2.78	MU	3.57	HU
Basic Presentation Structure	2.77	MU	3.51	HU
7. am much interested in purely printed text because though it's time consuming to read it's more comprehensive./ am much interested in printed text with graphics because it's more comprehensive thus it's timesaving.	2.93	MU	3.60	HU
8. do not trust learning materials with purely printed text whose references are not indicated./ do not trust learning materials with printed text and graphics whose references are not indicated.	2.61	MU	3.43	HU
9. I understand the message given by the purely printed text even without visuals./ I understand the message given by the printed text with graphics because of its visuals.	2.78	MU	3.50	HU
Memorability	2.77	MU	3.70	HU
10. purely printed text makes what I have learned from them more memorable./ visualizations in printed text with graphics make what I have learned from them more memorable.	2.94	MU	3.72	HU
11. remember information that I learned from purely printed text easier./ remember information that I learned from printed text with graphics easier	2.68	MU	3.65	HU
12. learn better critical information that are conveyed in purely printed text/ learn better critical information that are conveyed in printed text with graphics.	2.69	MU	3.74	HU
Role in Learning Process	2.82	MU	3.66	HU
13. prefer to read a purely printed text rather than reading a printed text with graphics to learn same subject./ prefer to read a printed text with graphics rather than reading a plain text to learn same subject.	2.83	MU	3.72	HU
14. prefer reading purely printed text before checking other sources concerning a subject I am trying to learn./ prefer reading printed text with graphics before checking other sources concerning a subject I am trying to learn.	2.79	MU	3.58	HU
15. first investigate or examine purely printed text to gain an idea about a subject I will be learning./ first investigate or examine printed text with graphics to gain an idea about a subject I will be learning.	2.85	MU	3.67	HU
Overall Mean	2.82	MU	3.62	HU

Note. Not Useful (NU: 1.00-1.75); Less Useful (LU: 1.76-2.50); Moderately Useful (MU: 2.51-3.25); High Useful (HU: 3.26-4.00)

Table 2 displays the means and usefulness of texts without graphics as assessed by the students. It could be gleaned from the table that in terms of informativeness, item 1 “purely printed text facilitates learning/ visual representation used in printed text with graphics facilitates learning” obtained the highest weighted mean of 2.93 described as “Moderately Useful” for no graphics and 3.76 described as “Highly Useful” for with graphics while item 3 “understand that, presentation of information using purely printed

text facilitates better learning/ understand that, printed text with graphics, presentation of information text facilitates better learning” obtained the lowest mean of 2.89 described as “Moderately Useful for no graphics and 3.60 for with graphics. The overall mean of 2.20 interpreted as “Less Useful” for no graphics and 3.78 interpreted with graphics as “Highly Useful”. This denotes that the learners appreciate more the informativeness of instructional materials if these are given with infographic.

The results correlated to what Nhan & Yen (2021) emphasized that Infographics in teaching-learning materials can be effective educational tools thanks to their ability to break complex information into easy-to-understand components and to make dense data engaging for the learning. That means providing words, images, and even interactive elements to help with attention, memory, and recall processes.

In terms of sharing, it could be extracted from the table that item 4 “am aware that, among the different sources of learning, I especially recommend purely printed text to people around me./ am aware that, among the different sources of learning, I especially recommend printed text with graphics to people around me” got the highest weighted mean of 2.89 interpreted as “Moderately Useful” for without graphics and 3.65 with graphics. On the other hand, item 6 “share the purely printed text that are prepared in compliance with copyrights. / share the printed text with graphics that are prepared in compliance with copyrights” got the lowest weighted mean of 2.78 interpreted as “Moderately Useful” for no graphics and 3.57 with graphics. This suggests that learners are more into sharing the instructional materials if these are with infographic and illustrations.

The findings are in conformity with what Pyankova (2020) had affirmed that the sharing of printed learning materials with or without graphics can be beneficial in terms of accessibility and portability. However, the cost of producing and distributing printed materials can be a barrier, and printed materials have limitations in terms of interactivity and customization.

As to Basic Presentation Structure, it could be gleaned from the table that item 7 “am much interested in purely printed text because though it’s time consuming to read it’s more comprehensive./ am much interested in printed text with graphics because it’s more comprehensive thus it’s timesaving” got the highest weighted mean of 2.93 interpreted as “Moderately Useful” for no graphics and 3.60 for with graphics while item 8 “do not trust learning materials with purely printed text whose references are not indicated./ do not trust learning materials with printed text and graphics whose references are not indicated.” got the lowest weighted mean of 2.61 described as “Moderately Useful” for without graphics and 3.43 described as “Highly Useful” for with graphics. This means that the basic presentation structure is more accurate and coherence when the instructional materials are presented with graphics.

According to Naparin & Saad (2017), learning materials with graphics often prove so effective in educational contexts because they use imagery to highlight, explain, or

enhance text-based information. They capture attention, convey information, and encourage data retention from many learners. That may make infographics ideal for teaching the basics of complicated processes or breaking down high-level data for general audiences.

In terms of Memorability, it could be manifested from the table that item 10 “purely printed text makes what I have learned from them more memorable./ visualizations in printed text with graphics make what I have learned from them more memorable” attained the highest mean of 2.94 expressed as “Moderately Useful” for without graphics and 3.72 expressed as “Highly Useful” for with graphics while item 11 “. remember information that I learned from purely printed text easier./ . remember information that I learned from printed text with graphics easier” attained the lowest weighted mean of 2.68 expressed as “Moderately Useful for with graphics and 3.65 for with graphics.

Alsuliman, et al. (2019) in their study had accentuated that most people make sense of visual material much faster than other methods. Learners wants to remember the content, especially if it is fantastic. It is part of the lead nurturing process and the teacher want it to make the learners think and stick in their brains

As to Role in Learning Process, it could be gleaned from the table that item 15 “first investigate or examine purely printed text to gain an idea about a subject I will be learning./ first investigate or examine printed text with graphics to gain an idea about a subject I will be learning” tallied the highest mean of 2.85 described as “Moderately Useful” for without graphics and 3.67 described as “Highly Useful” for with graphics. This means that for the learners instructional materials with graphics are relevance to their learnings in the modular distance modality.

The overall mean of learners’ assessment is 2.82 interpreted as “Moderately Useful” for without graphics and 3.62 interpreted as “Highly Useful” for with graphics. This means that instructional materials in the modular distance learning can be engaging and useful if they are given with infographic presentations.

As underscored by Pyankova (2020) in his research, he stressed that an infographic can help learners about an important lesson while teaching them how and why there is a need to apply what they have learned. These learning materials can be great tools to help students think creatively and learn new ways to apply their skills and knowledge in their day-to-day living. Creating a visual guide of tips or tricks for how to complete a project or meet a goal could be beneficial to the students. Moreover, infographics have the ability to break complex information into easy-to-understand components and to make even intricate lessons engaging. Whether the teachers want to communicate with their learners about the lesson the use of instructional materials with graphics is so effective in an educational context in the modular distance learning.

The role of graphics in the learning process can be quite significant. Graphics can enhance comprehension, aid in retention of information, and promote engagement and interest in the subject matter. It is important to consider the role of graphics in the learning

process when designing instructional materials. Incorporating appropriate visuals can help learners understand, retain, and engage with the content more effectively.

Table 3. Significant Difference on the Usefulness of English Language Materials if Students are Categorized according to Grades

Grade	Means	p- values	Decision on H ₀	Difference
No Graphics				
Advanced (90-100)	1.78	<.001	Rejected	Significant
Proficient (85-89)	2.47			
Approaching Proficiency (80-84)	2.80			
Beginning Proficiency (75-79)	3.54			
With Graphics				
Advanced (90-100)	4.00	<.001	Rejected	Significant
Proficient (85-89)	4.00			
Approaching Proficiency (80-84)	3.93			
Beginning Proficiency (75-79)	3.15			

Note: Significance Level $\alpha = .05$

Table 3 presented the significance of differences in the usefulness of English language learning materials based on their grades. It could be extracted from the table that advanced students gave the lowest rating of 1.78 while students having the beginning proficiency had the highest rating of 3.54 to the texts with no graphics. The pattern of ratings can also be noted that as the students' grade levels got higher, their ratings to the texts without graphics decreased.

In the One-Way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA), the computed p-value was less than .001 which led to the rejection of the null hypothesis of no significant difference among the ratings of the students to the texts without graphics when students are grouped according to the grade levels. This showed enough evidence to support the research hypothesis (H1) advanced in this study that claimed that the ratings of the students differ significantly in at least one grade level. When Scheffe's post hoc test was used to determine which ratings of the students differ significantly, it was found out that the students having a beginning proficiency gave the significantly highest mean compared to the students of the higher grade levels. In contrast, the advanced students gave the significantly lowest mean ratings to the texts without graphics compared to the students belonging to the lower grade levels. The proficient students and those belonging to the approaching proficiency levels group together as having significantly similar ratings but are significantly different from the other two groups. This means that instructional English materials have been observed as a powerful strategy to bring about effective teaching and learning in modular distance learning. As an English teacher in the public schools, the importance of quality and adequate English instructional materials in teaching and learning can occur through their effective utilization during classroom teaching to make the learning more interesting and memorable especially in this time of the pandemic.

On the other hand, pertaining to the texts with graphics, Table 3 showed the pattern of ratings that increase as the grade levels of the students also increase. The students belonging to the lowest grade level of beginning proficiency got the lowest level. In contrast, the advanced and the proficient students gave the highest rating of 4.00 and who were closely followed by the students belonging to the approaching proficiency. From One-Way ANOVA, since the p-value was less than .001, the null hypotheses of no significant differences among the ratings of the students to the texts with graphics was rejected. So, there was enough evidences to support the research hypothesis (H2) in this study claiming that at least one grade level of students significantly differ from others.

When Scheffe's post hoc test was used to determine grade levels of the students that differ, it was found out that the students having a beginning proficiency level gave the significantly lowest mean compared to the students of the higher grade levels. In contrast, the students from the higher grade levels group together as having significantly similar ratings. This suggests that the grade of the learners correlates on the instructional materials given by the teacher. It is important to note that as an English teacher, learning occurs better when text with graphics are given to learners resulting to a better academic performance in English subject.

According to Tety (2016), English language instructional materials include books, modules and learning activity sheets. He further opines that the availability, adequacy and relevance of these instructional materials in classrooms can influence quality teaching, which can have positive effect on students' learning and academic performance. The insight from Tety (2016) on linking instructional resources to students' academic performance serve critical in the provision of quality education. The title of this thesis, role of instructional materials in academic performance in community secondary schools in Rombo district originates from such ideas. Efficiency and high productivity in teaching and learning transaction. In my views, start from the access to quality and adequate instructional materials, and these should be prepared well before the class interaction.

Moreover, writing on the role of English instructional materials with graphics in teaching and learning, Sephania, et. al. (2017) commented that English Education program cannot be taught effectively without the existence of printed learning materials. This is because instructional materials help those who learn to develop problem-solving skills, scientific attitudes, reading, writing, and comprehension. Elaborating further on the same point, Akiri (2013) emphasize that when English language instructional materials are provided to meet relative needs of teaching process, students will have access to the reference materials mentioned by the teacher, and also each student will be able to learn at his or her own pace. The overall result is that students will perform much better.

Learning materials with graphics created for educational purposes allow information to be presented within a particular context. Yildirim, et. al. (2016) argued that language materials with graphics are useful in supporting the development of students. In addition, language materials with graphics are considered to be an effective communication tool for communication with the information. The instructional effects of

visuals are on the upper level when they are prepared according to the scheme of learners. Similarly, learning with language materials with graphics may allow learners to understand the information in an organized way and form the basis for schemes needed to be created in the minds of individuals.

Meanwhile, students with beginning proficiency who choose the purely printed text simply because they do not want any complications with supplementation of graphics or picture. Students seem to be confused and unable to understand when utilizing English language materials with graphics.

However, the findings of this study negates with what Yıldırım (2016) had found out that, it is important to note that the learners with fairly-satisfactory performance like learning materials with graphics while advanced learners find the usefulness of both learning materials with or without graphics. Therefore, he concluded that learning materials with graphics and without graphics are relevant to all learners as far as their learning achievements are concerned. These materials may help students to improve their critical thinking, analysis and making synthesis skills in addition to creating instructional design skills.

Table 4. Significant Difference on the Usefulness of English Language Materials as Assessed by the Teachers and Students

Participant	Means	p- values	Decision on H ₀	Difference
No Graphics				
Teachers	2.20	<.01	Rejected	Significant
Students	2.82			
With Graphics				
Teachers	3.78	.19	Not Rejected	Not Significant
Students	3.62			

Note: Significance Level $\alpha = .05$

Table 4 displayed the means, p-values and significance of differences on the assessments of teachers and students. It could be gleaned from Table 4 that 2.20 as the mean of teachers compared to 2.82 of the students. From the Independent Two-Sample t test, since the computed p-value was less than .01, the null hypothesis of no significant difference between the teachers' and the students' ratings of the texts without graphics was rejected. So, there was enough evidence to support the research third hypothesis (H3) advanced in this study claiming that the teachers and the students differ significantly in their ratings to the texts without graphics.

More specifically, the students gave significantly higher ratings than the teachers to the texts without graphics. This means that teachers have different expectations or preferences when it comes to the usefulness of English language materials compared to their students. It may also indicate that there is a need for better communication and collaboration between teachers and students to ensure that the materials used in teaching meet the needs and expectations of both parties. Furthermore, this finding also

suggest that there is a need for further research into how English language materials can be improved to better serve the needs of both teachers and students. By identifying the reasons behind the differences in perception between teachers and students, educators can work towards creating more effective and engaging materials that will benefit both groups. Moreover, these materials help to increase active participation in the learning process while saving teacher's energy, reducing the teacher centeredness in teaching.

On the other hand, on the text with graphics, though the teachers gave a higher mean rating of 3.78 that the students' 3.62, they did not have significantly different ratings since their p-value of .19 was greater than the level of significance. So, the null hypothesis of no significant difference was not rejected. So, there was enough evidence to support the fourth research hypothesis (H4) advanced in this study claiming that the teachers and the students differ significantly in their ratings to the texts with graphics. This implies that the students learned better when the instructional materials are supplemented with graphics. Greater understanding is achieved by the students in English language especially in the use of modules in this time of the pandemic.

The results coincide with what Alos et al. (2015) stressed that English language instructional materials with graphics are essential because they help teachers and learners avoid overemphasis on recitation and rote learning that can easily dominate a lesson. These materials allow learners to have practical experiences which help them to develop skills and concepts and to work in a variety of ways. Ajoke (2017) also observes that instructional materials help teachers to teach conveniently and the learners to learn easily without stress. She asserts that instructional materials have direct contact with all the sense organs of the students. Lee & Mahmoudi-Gahrouei (2020) support this view by reiterating that, instructional materials are very significant learning and teaching tools. They add that there is need for teachers to find necessary and relevant English language instructional materials with graphics to complement classroom interaction and textbooks in order to broaden and arouse students' interests in the subject.

Although teachers use different instructional materials to motivate learning by using textbooks, charts, models, graphics, real objects as well as improvised materials. The success of achieving what they are met to achieve in an instructional situation depend on the suitability of the instructional materials, adequacy and effective utilization of the materials. The effectiveness of instructional materials in promoting students' academic performance in teaching and learning is indisputable. It provides the much needed sensory experiences needed by the learners for an effective and meaningful behavioural change. Instructional materials are meant to improve the quality of education for effective academic performance of students in schools.

The use of English instructional materials with graphics helps meet tech literacy standards. These materials also help students improve their research chops and find trustworthy sources of information. Moreover, these materials exhibit their understanding in English and other related subjects in different ways. These also make them more

creative by shifting their perspectives. Consequently, these materials help teachers save time in creating visual aids, particularly if they use infographic templates

Findings

The detailed analysis of the data gathered revealed the following findings:

1. The teachers' assessment of the usefulness of printed materials in terms of "informativeness" obtained the highest mean which is interpreted as "Moderately Useful" without graphics and "Highly Useful" with graphics. Meanwhile, "The role in Learning Process" as its aspect, was perceived as "Less Useful" without graphics and "Highly Useful" with graphics. The overall tally was perceived as "Moderately Useful" without graphics and "Highly Useful" with graphics.
2. The learners' assessment of the usefulness of printed materials in terms of "informativeness" obtained the highest mean which is interpreted as "Moderately Useful" without graphics and "Highly Useful" with graphics. On the other hand, the "Basic Presentation Structure" as its aspect, was perceived as "Moderately Useful" without graphics and "Highly Useful" with graphics. The overall tally was perceived as "Moderately Useful" without graphics and "Highly Useful" with graphics.
3. The advanced students gave the lowest rating while students with beginning proficiency had the highest rating for the texts with no graphics because students with beginning proficiency choose the purely printed text simply because they do not want any complications with the supplementation of graphics or pictures. Students seem to be confused and unable to understand when utilizing English language materials with graphics.
4. The pattern of ratings can also be noted that as the students' grade levels got higher, their ratings to the texts without graphics decreased. The results led to the rejection of the null hypothesis of no significant difference in the assessment of the students to the texts without graphics. Moreover, it was also found that the students having a beginning proficiency gave the significantly highest mean compared to the students of the higher grade levels. In contrast, the advanced students gave the significantly lowest mean ratings to the texts without graphics compared to the students belonging to the lower grade levels. The proficient students and those belonging to the approaching proficiency levels group together as having significantly similar ratings but are significantly different from the other two groups. The null hypothesis of no significant difference in the assessment of the students to the texts with graphics was rejected. Furthermore, there was enough evidence to support the research hypothesis in this study claiming that at least one grade level of students significantly differs from others. In addition, it was

found that the students having a beginning proficiency level gave the significantly lowest mean compared to the students of the higher grade levels.

5. The null hypothesis of no significant difference between the teachers' and the students' assessment of the texts without graphics was rejected. So, there was enough evidence to support the research hypothesis advanced in this study claiming that the teachers and the students differ significantly in their ratings of the texts without graphics. On the other hand, on the text with graphics, though the teachers gave a higher mean rating, they did not have a significantly different assessment. There was enough evidence to support the research hypothesis advanced in this study claiming that the teachers and the students differ significantly in their assessment of the texts with graphics.

Conclusions

Instructional materials play a crucial role in keeping students engaged in modular distance learning. The type of materials used in instruction can significantly impact a students' motivation, interest, and learning outcomes. Instructional materials can be useful in keeping students engaged in distance learning, but their effectiveness depends on the students' preferences, proficiency level, and access to technology. It is essential for teachers to provide a variety of English language instructional materials that cater to students' different proficiency levels, preferences, and needs. By doing so, educators can keep students engaged, enhance their learning experiences, and promote positive academic outcomes in modular distance learning.

Recommendations

The following recommendations are suggested for consideration based on the study's conclusions and findings:

1. Enhancing English Language Materials for Teachers. English teachers need to be informed about the usefulness of English language materials in modular distance learning. They need to employ varied strategies and give attention to the existing problems that arise in the new normal education. Teachers need to provide English language materials that are supplemented by graphics. They need to provide varied English language materials that are not limited to textbooks and printed materials but also infographics.

2. Strengthening Students' Appreciation of English Materials. Students need to appreciate the English learning materials with or without graphics. They should be encouraged to develop a deeper appreciation for the English language and its intricacies, which can be achieved through exposure to various forms of language input, such as printed English learning materials with or without graphics.

3. Improving Parents' English Language Support Skills. Parents need to improve their language skills, specifically in the English language, to effectively assist their children with

their learning activities. The use of graphics in teaching materials can enhance the learning experience and make the content more accessible to students. Thus, parents must also have basic skills in interpreting and explaining graphic materials to their children.

4. Developing Strategic School Plans for English Instruction. School heads may need to invest more time and resources in creating effective plans and activities to address the gap in English language materials in public schools. This could involve training teachers on effective teaching strategies for remote learning, developing new curriculum materials tailored to modular distance instruction, and investing in technology and resources that can enhance the quality of instruction. They also need to ensure that secondary students are equipped with the necessary English language skills to succeed in academic and professional settings.

5. Enhancing Policy and Curriculum Support from DepEd. DepEd officials should recognize the importance of improving English language materials in modular distance learning and understand that effective planning and curriculum enhancement are necessary to achieve this goal. They have access to baseline data that can inform their decision-making process, and they are expected to use this information to create targeted interventions that address the specific needs of students.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The study strictly followed ethical standards to protect the rights and welfare of all participants. Permissions were obtained from school authorities, and informed consent was secured from teachers, learners, and parents or guardians. Participation was voluntary, with the right to withdraw at any time. Confidentiality and anonymity were maintained, and all data were used solely for academic purposes and stored securely. These measures ensured that the entire research process upheld privacy, dignity, and ethical integrity.

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